

Topic similarities in the works of Uzbek modern women writers

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Abstract: The importance of women literature and the themes they have in their works are similar and different in the same time. Lately, the role of women in poetry and prose is becoming more and more important, since the topics they are working on are interesting and appealing to the reading. When it comes to modern Uzbek women writers, it is worth to mention the names such as Zulfiya, Khalima Khudoyberdiyeva, Zebo Mirzo, Khosiyat Rustamova, Khalima Akhmedova, the authors of incomparable works. In the following article, in turn, we will provide more detailed information about these representatives of Uzbek modern literature, and we will try to make some conclusions about the differences in their creative works.

Key words: literary criticism, Uzbek literature, separation, feminism, traditions

Introduction.

While creating a work every single writer needs to consider the essence of the time, era, the crucial issues of that time, and of course, the interest in the reader. Otherwise, the works, the topics discussed can't carry an important message. If it fails to have an influence on the person reading and analyzing the literary works, it means the writer is inattentively using the canon, ready material, instead of being himself. Themes which are described in the work decide if the writer is going to be successful or can't be recognized as a good writer. It is very important to find a way to the readers mind, and sing the topics which are in their hearts. In Uzbek modern literature there are several women writers who could accomplish this task, some of them are Zulfiya, Khalima Khudoyberdiyeva, Zebo Mirzo, Khosiyat Rustamova, Khalima Akhmedova, and so on.

Main body.

Zulfiya is considered to be the center of the modern women literature in Uzbek poetry. Her works were always appreciated for the reason that she could bring the message of the Uzbek women in her poems, she could say the words in most Uzbek women's minds through her poems. One of the scholars, G. Umurova who has worked a lot to learn Zulfiya's literary works, considers it appropriate to study the subject-content of the poetess's poetry based on the following six principles in her monograph "Artistic World of the Poet Zulfiya":

1. Poems on the theme of love;
2. Poems on the theme of the Motherland;
3. Poems reflecting nature and human relations;
4. Poems on mixed topics;
5. Poems on the theme of death;
6. Poems on journalistic (Publicist) topics.

In her opinion, the second, fourth and sixth principles of the poet's aesthetic world and artistic thinking acquired a real essence. The border of eternity and non-existence is clarified

when the mood of a flood of emotions, pain and emigration, loneliness and sadness rise to the level of a poetic image. Also, expressiveness and musicality create a uniqueness in love poems. Here you can read an extract from her poem "Bahor kechasi" ("Spring night") which is mainly about the description of the nature:

Ko'k baxmalga gullar burkangan,
Lab ochmagan, bulbul o'pmagan
Ko'zim tushdi olma guliga,
Dedim: taqşam eng go'zal birin –
So'ylab bersa... mening chakkamda
Dilbarligin, go'zallik sirin.

Khalima Khudoyberdiyeva's poems can be called the biography of her troubled soul. Halima Khudoyberdiyeva's work began in the 60s, and until now she has created more than twenty poetry collections, epics and journalistic articles. In particular, her "Ilk muhabbat" ("First Love") (1968), "Oq olmalar" ("White Apples") (1973), "Chaman" (1974), "Suyanch tog'larim" ("My Mountains of Support") (1976), "Bobo quyosh" ("Grandfather Sun") (1977), "Issiq qor" ("Hot Snow") (1979), "Sadoqat" ("Loyalty") (1983), "Muqaddas ayol" ("Holy Woman") (1987), "Yuragimning og'riq nuqtalari" ("The Painful Points of My Heart") (1991), "Hurlik Oti" ("Freedom flame") (1993), "Bu kunlarga yetganlar bor" ("There Are Those Who Have Reached These Days") (1994), "To'marisning aytgani" ("Tomaris's sayings") (1996) have become the intellectual property of a wide readership.

The main passion of Halima Khudoyberdiyeva's work is love for the motherland and feelings of loyalty similarly to the other writers who we discuss in this article. Her first collection "Ilk Muhabbat" ("First Love") already showed this pathos identity:

Qon aslan yorug'lik. Yorug'lan, tiz cho'k,
Asl mard Vatanga tiz cho'kib o'tar.
Qancha qoning bo'lsa, Vatan uchun to'k,
Qancha joning bo'lsa, Vatanni ko'tar!

Like her peers, Halima Akhmedova spoke about love, mother, Motherland, and nature. While writing these topics, you can feel and perceive the spirit of Cho'lpon in the verses he created. An example of our opinion:

Xayol kechalari qismat bog'ida,
Yolg'izlikda adashgan manmu?
Olloh, kaftlaringda bir kuni
Maysa bo'lib egilamanmu?

Yomg'ir kabi yog'ilsa jonim,
Qarog'larim bo'larmikin jom?
Tig' urilgan bag'rim qoniga
Yuragini chayarmu oqshom?

Zebo Mirzo entered Uzbek literature at the end of the 20th century with the poetry collection "Tun malikasi" ("Queen of the Night"). She is also the author of poetry collections such as "Ajr" (1997), "Nur kukunlari" (2004), "Ishq" (2012). The poet considers creativity to be a conversation with inspiration. Lines created from inspiration sometimes turn into reflection, sometimes into

tears, sometimes into prayer and even rebellion. This is how the poet interpreted the work. The characteristic of his interpretation is embodied in verses as a criterion of artistry.

Zebo Mirzo writes in various genres, forms, and themes, but the status of poems on love topics is high in her work:

Yuragimning ostidami,
Yo ko'kda, tun pallasi.
Sarv-u suman soyasida
Hurlar aytar allasin,
Malaklarning qanotida
Nurday uxlar bir go'dak,
Eshitganday bo'laman
Shirin-shirin nafasini...

Conclusion.

In conclusion, themes discussed and described in the works of modern Uzbek women literature are similar to one another. They mostly write on the topic of love to the motherland, the depiction of nature, love life, the description and feelings of women. People of all genders and ages can find universal theme while reading their poems. The topics are very usual for Uzbek literature, however, they carry a different message which makes them appealing. Modern Uzbek literature is taking a different shape, and partially it is because of the above mentioned woman writers such as Zulfiya, Khalima Khudiyberdiyeva, Zebo Mirzo, Khalima Akhmedova. They will continue to create abundant of works that will encourage young and old generation with the help of poems.

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